

PARENTAL INVOLVEMENT IN BRIGADA ESKWELA AND SCHOOL PERFORMANCE

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ABSTRACT

This study dealt on parental involvement in Brigada Eskwela and school performance. It aimed to determine how parental involvement affects the school performance during the school year 2020-2021. The study used the descriptive correlation design and the researcher made a survey questionnaire instrument used. The respondents of the study were 104 students of Dolores Macasaet National High School. The data gathered from the respondents were put in a coding format and the result obtained were presented in a tabular form, analyzed and interpreted using the following statistical technique and procedures. Descriptive statistics such as frequency, percentage, mean, and standard deviation were used for the analysis. The parental involvement in Brigada Eskwela is often participated in all components; including level of parent participation / involvement, attitudes of parents toward Brigada Eskwela, cooperation and nature of involvement. The school performance is performed very good in all components; including improved facilities and community services as to health, literacy and livelihood program. Relative to the parental involvement and school performance, there is significant correlation at all computed r value. From the findings of the study, the this conclusion is drawn. There is significant relationship between parental involvement and school performance. Thus, null hypothesis posited is not supported. Based on the conclusions of the study, the following recommendations are offered: 1. School principal is recommended to consider the parent involvement in planning, utilization and evaluation of such activities, including Brigada Eskwela. 2. Parents are recommended to be participative in various school activities such as Brigada Eskwela. 3. Teachers are recommended to function as the first hand concern person in utilization of school activities such as Brigada Eskwela. 4. Students are recommended to support the Brigada Eskwela program of the school, aiming to the benefits of learners. 5. Researchers' are recommended to study the result of this paper and propagate same study that benefits school and learners.

Keywords: Brigada Eskwela, parental involvement, Descriptive statistics, school performance